

DETERIORATION OF WATER AND SOIL QUALITY ALONG YAMUNA RIVERBED IN THE NATIONAL CAPITAL REGION

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ABSTRACT

Yamuna, a river, revered by millions of people, is losing its purity and serenity as it flows along the historical cities of Panipat, Delhi, Mathura, Agra, and Kanpur to finally converge with the Ganges in Allahabad. It is the lifeline of the capital of India, but is struggling against a seemingly lost battle for its survival. It is a bed for receiving wastes from Industries, power plants, drainage, municipal garbage, e-wastes, agriculture etc. which makes it unsuitable for any purpose. The soil samples from the bank of Yamuna river at various sites were collected and their chemical parameters- namely pH, conductivity, salinity, organic matter, calcium carbonate content, water-soluble sulphate, water-soluble chloride, cation exchange capacity were analysed. Samples were also analysed for Ca, Mg, Na, K and heavy metal detection of Cu, Fe, Zn, Ni, Mn and Cr was carried out by atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The results show large deviation from the healthy soil indicating huge amount of pollutants leading to deterioration of water and soil quality.

Key words : Yamuna, pollution, chemical parameters, heavy metals, pollutant, soil,

1. Introduction:

Yamuna river is the largest tributary of the Ganga. It emerges from the Yamunotri glacier near Bandar Punch (380 59' N 780 27' E) in the lower Himalayas at an elevation of about 6320 meters in the district of Uttarkashi (Uttaranchal). The path of the Yamuna River covers parts of the states of Uttaranchal, Himachal Pradesh, Haryana, Rajasthan, Delhi, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh [1]. The river Yamuna covers a distance of about 1370 km in the plain from the Saharanpur district of Uttar Pradesh to its convergence with river Ganga at Allahabad. Till the early twentieth century, the Yamuna water was transparent as clear blue but in the present era, Yamuna has become one of the most polluted rivers in the world [2-4].

For decades, it is seen that civilizations have flourished on the banks of rivers. River's urbanization and Industrialization are the basic parameters for the economic growth of a nation. But these give rise to useless by-products which are a huge source of pollution for the soil and water resources. As the effluent discharges from factories and industries are ultimately discharged either on the landfill sites or thrown directly into water bodies, the rivers and soils become highly contaminated [5-7]. This also gives rise to many environmental problems affecting the growth of flora and fauna of the region.

The Yamuna becomes particularly polluted in the downstream of New Delhi, the capital of India, which dumps more than half of its waste, into this river. A study report of 2016 shows that there is almost 100% urbanization of Yamuna River as it traverses through the National Capital Region of Delhi [8]. Waste disposal in Delhi starts from Wazirabad, from where Yamuna enters the capital city. Domestic sources contribute about 85% of river pollution (CWC 2009). These include dumping of domestic garbage which is on a continual rise due to increasing density of population on the banks of river practising poor sanitation, e-wastes, agricultural run-offs, oil spills, dead bodies, cattle washings, disposing untreated industrial wastes, sewage, drainages, immersing of idols, undetected heavy metals etc making the river highly toxic [9-11].

The present study includes collection of soil samples from bank of Yamuna river at specific sites and analysis of its physico-chemical characteristics as well as detection of heavy metals in the sample.

2. Methodology:

2.1 Location : The study location involved collecting of water and soil samples from banks of Yamuna river at various places as listed in the Table 1:

Table 1: Labelling of samples and geographical mapping.

S.no	Sample no.	Sampling Location
1	A-1	Up Stream of Wazirabad Barrage, Jagatpur Village (L/B) (Sample from agricultural village)
2	A-2	Down Stream Wazirabad Barrage, Right Bank (L/B)

3	A-3	Upstream of ITO Barrage opposite Rajghat power station near Geeta Colony fly over (R/B)
4	A-4	Upstream of ITO Barrage opposite Rajghat power station near Shantivan drain
5	A-5	Rajghat power station, Ash pond
6	A-6	ITO barrage upstream (left bank)
7	A-7	ITO barrage upstream left bank 200 m away from river side near hathishala
8	A-8	ITO barrage downstream Right bank opposite Indraprastha power station, near metro rail bridge
9	A-9	Nizamuddin barrage, downstream (R/B)
10	A-10	Okhla barrage, downstream (L/B),Kalindikunj

2.2 Visual observations

The Following, real-time pictures were taken from various sites of sample collection. These pictures are a clear indication of massive pollution in the Yamuna river and its banks.

Figure 1: Pictures showing pollution in Yamuna River and its banks

2.3 Sample collection and processing:

Sampling was done from the destined places by first removing the surface weeds and dirt, and then digging around 6 to 8 inches deep using a spade and shovel. These were collected and labelled properly in transparent plastic zip pouches, and were taken immediately to the laboratories. These samples were then air-dried for 2-4 days in the tray, at room temperature and then after initial processing, was used for carrying out various physico-chemical analysis by volumetric and instrumental analytical methods as per IS-2720 according to BIS, and ASTM standards.

2.4 Methods of Chemical analysis of soil and Instrumentation:

The chemical analysis of soil was done as per procedures mentioned in IS-2720 which included:

1. pH measurement was done by a potentiometric method using portable and Multiparameter instrument.
2. Conductivity (Total Soluble salts)- Portable conductivity meter and Multiparameter instrument
3. Calcium Carbonate Content: Acid-base titration using NaOH and HCl
4. Water Soluble Chloride- Precipitation titration using silver nitrate and potassium chromate indicator.
5. Water Soluble Sulphate - Gravimetric estimation using barium chloride reagent
6. Organic Matter- Redox titration using potassium dichromate as an oxidizing agent.
7. Calcium and Magnesium - Complexometric titration using EDTA.
8. Sodium and Potassium- Using a flame photometer
9. Cation exchange capacity - Using the Ammonium acetate method
10. Heavy metals - Using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS)

3. Results and Discussion:

Table 2 shows the result of various Physicochemical properties of different samples collected from different sites on the bank of the river Yamuna.

Sample no.	pH	Conductivity $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$	Salinity	CaCO ₃ Content	Organic Matter % by wt	Water soluble Chloride % by wt	Water soluble sulphate % by wt	Cation Exchange Capacity meq/100g
A-1	7.58	130	0.1	0.49	0.28	0.025	0.020	5.2
A-2	7.25	169	0.1	1.8	0.31	0.002	0.029	6.4
A-3	6.65	240	0.2	0.5	0.56	0.065	0.048	8.0

A-4	6.78	290	0.2	0.8	1.08	0.072	.051	6.3
A-5	6.90	352	0.3	1.8	0.10	0.09	0.105	5.0
A-6	7.68	332	0.3	2.9	1.88	0.082	0.078	7.8
A-7	8.05	299	0.2	4.8	1.15	0.067	0.068	12
A-8	7.24	383	0.4	3.8	3.55	0.105	0.120	10.0
A-9	8.35	455	0.5	5.2	4.32	0.125	0.138	8.2
A-10	8.86	560	0.7	7.8	6.4	0.186	0.198	8.0

Table 2: Chemical analysis of soil samples at different locations.

It is observed that there is an increase in the concentration of various chemical parameters starting from Wazirabad to Nizamuddin barrage. pH is observed to show alkaline nature in almost all the samples except a few locations near the Rajghat power plant where it falls below 7.0 showing a slightly acidic nature which might be due to mixing of effluents from the thermal power plant into the river directly and near ash pond of Rajghat power plant. The over all pH range was observed to lie between 6.65 to 8.86. This is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Variation in pH of various samples

The value of conductivity (total soluble salt contents) was also observed to show an increase in value on coming down along the riverside. The conductivity values of blank soil samples are reasonably lower in comparison to contaminated sites. The increase in salt content is due to the

mixing of sewage through various drains directly without treatment. The conductivity values ranges from 130 to 560 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$. This is expressed graphically in Figure 3.

Figure 3:
Variation in conductivity of various samples

The value of calcium carbonate content is low in blank soil. However at contaminated sites significant values are observed. That is due to various construction activities going on near river bed which results in accumulation of construction material. Due to high total soluble salts values, the contaminated soil shows little saline character. The variation in salinity and calcium carbonate content is shown graphically in figures 4 and 5 respectively.

Figure 4: Variation in salinity of various samples

Figure 5: Variation in calcium carbonate content of various samples

The significant deposition of organic matter contents are observed at contaminated sites due to heavy sewage accumulation along river bed. The highest value of organic matter value observed is 6.4 % by wt which is above normal limits. The variation of organic matter content is expressed graphically in Figure 6. The water-soluble chloride and water soluble sulphate levels also show increasing trends along downstream which is directly related to increasing soluble salt contents. The values are significant in view of their impact on concrete structures and steel reinforcement. These are depicted collectively in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Variation in organic matter content, water soluble chloride & water soluble sulphate in various samples.

The values of cation exchange capacity are comparatively lower compared to blank soil samples which shows the leaching behaviour of contaminated soils.

Figure 7: Variation in Cation exchange capacity of various samples

Sample No	Ca mEq/L	Mg mEq/L	Na mEq/L	K mEq/L	% Na	Sodium absorption ratio (SAR)
A-1	1.0	0.8	0.517	0.349	19.3%	0.448
A-2	1.2	0.7	1.313	0.533	35.05%	1.347
A-3	1.52	1.6	2.12	0.879	34.6%	1.697
A-4	2.0	1.0	1.456	0.99	26.74%	1.189
A-5	1.8	0.2	0.37	0.482	3.75%	0.37
A-6	2.41	1.4	3.07	0.682	40.5%	2.224
A-7	1.0	0.8	1.069	0.269	10.3%	1.126

A-8	2.05	2.2	2.261	1.246	30.11%	1.559
A-9	1.95	1.8	3.113	0.441	42.6%	2.260
A-10	3.0	3.6	5.017	1.012	39.72%	2.762

Table 3: Na, K, Ca, Mg, % Na and Sodium absorption ratio for soil sample at different sites

Table 3 compares different metal ions, namely Na, K, Ca, Mg, % Na and Sodium absorption ratio for soil samples at different sites of Yamuna bed starting from Jagatpur to Okhla barrage.

Figure 8: Variation in Na, K, Ca, and Mg in various samples

The value of sodium in saturated extract is observed to be nearly 40% at 2-3 locations. The higher sodium level results in deterioration of soil's physical structure by deflocculation. It is shown graphically in Figure 8, 9 and 10.

Figure 9: Variation in % Na of various samples

Figure 10: Variation in Sodium absorption ratio (SAR) of various samples

The presence of heavy metals were analyzed at selected locations. The values along Yamuna river bed down to Okhla shows significant increase in concentration when compared to blank soil samples.

Sample No	Trace Metal Analysis, mg/L					
	Cu	Ni	Mn	Cr	Zn	Fe
A-1	0.010	0.0	0.004	0.0	0.021	0.002
A-2	0.018	0.0	0.046	0.008	0.060	0.045
A-8	0.032	.010	0.053	0.010	0.074	0.062
A-9	0.060	0.031	0.18	0.03	0.23	0.12
A-10	0.089	0.06	0.53	0.05	0.89	0.48

Table 4: Heavy metal analysis for soil samples at selected locations of Yamuna river bed

Figure 15: Analysis of Zn for selected samples

Figure 16: Analysis of Fe for selected

Conclusion : The analysis shows that the effect of various contaminants are quite significant, which is depicted in the form of change in pH, organic matter, water soluble chloride, water soluble sulphates and total soluble salt content. The results of metal ion concentration shows an increase in amount of Na, K, Ca and Mg from wazirabad to Okhla. Similarly the heavy metal analysis of Cu, Fe, Zn, Ni, Cr and Mn shows a considerable elevation in their concentration suggesting the increase of pollutant levels in Yamuna as it traverses down towards Okhla. The rising contamination in Yamuna is a serious threat to mankind. It is high time that the people of this city start realizing the alarming condition of this river and work sincerely on improving the water quality of this pious river.

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CONFLICT OF AUTHORS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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